

ANALYSIS ON THE LOAD TRANSFER TO MISALIGNED WHISKERS IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The load transfer mechanism from matrix to whiskers in metal matrix composite was investigated by analyzing the load transfer efficiency at whisker/matrix interfaces. The stress acting on the surface of a whisker was divided into two components, which are longitudinal and transverse to the whisker axis. The stress transferred on a whisker was calculated by solving the differential equations for force equilibrium in longitudinal and transverse directions. An effective aspect ratio was suggested as a new parameter indicating the load transfer efficiency of a misaligned whisker. The effective aspect ratio contributed from the whole distributed whiskers in metal matrix composites was formulated as a function of average aspect ratio and misalignment angle of whiskers. A generalized shear-lag model based on the analysis of the load transfer of misaligned whiskers predicted the tensile strengths of metal matrix composites more accurately than the modified shear-lag model.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composites, whiskers, load transfer, generalized shear-lag model, effective aspect ratio, misalignment angle, interface

INTRODUCTION

The addition of SiC reinforcements in aluminum matrix results in an increase of mechanical properties, such as tensile strength, elastic modulus and creep resistance [1,2]. The increase of mechanical properties of metal matrix composites(MMCs) is explained by the two strengthening mechanisms. One is the strengthening mechanism due to the load transfer from soft matrix to rigid reinforcement [3]. The other is the strengthening mechanism by the increase of dislocation density due to the mismatch of thermal expansion coefficients between matrix and reinforcement [4]. The two strengthening mechanisms influence on the tensile strength of MMCs independently [4,5]. The effects of dislocation density on tensile strength were effectively formulated by Hall-Petch equation [5] or other equations [6,7]. The shear-lag model was proposed by Piggot [3] to analyze the load transfer effect of fibers in composite materials.

The shear-lag model was modified by Nardone and Prewo [8] into the form which takes into account the tensile load transfer from the matrix to the discontinuous reinforcement. The modified shear-lag model describes the strengthening of metal matrix composites more precisely than the shear-lag model, especially for the composites containing reinforcement with small aspect ratio. However, the modified shear-lag model often overestimates the

strengthening effect in longitudinal direction and underestimates in transverse direction [5]. This discrepancy in the strengthening effect is originated from the assumption of perfect alignment of reinforcement in the modified shear-lag model. In our previous works [9,10], the load transfer efficiency of misaligned whiskers was analyzed and could reasonably correlated with the creep behavior of metal matrix composites.

In this paper, a generalized shear-lag model was proposed through the theoretical modeling of the load transfer mechanism of misaligned whiskers in metal matrix composite. The tensile strengths of metal matrix composites were estimated by the proposed model and were compared with the measured tensile strengths in longitudinal and transverse directions.

THEORETICAL MODEL

Load Transfer on a Misaligned Whisker

In our previous investigations [9,10], the load transfer at the side surface of a whisker was analysed. When the aspect ratio of a whisker is relatively small, the load transfer contribution at the end surface of whisker need to be also considered. Therefore, the load transfer efficiency was analyzed considering the load transfer on both side surface and end surface of a misaligned whisker as shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 : The analysis of the stresses acting on a whisker aligned with misorientation angle θ from the loading axis

Fig.2: Schematic diagram showing the longitudinal stresses on thin slice of a misaligned whisker

As the differential longitudinal tensile stress, $d\sigma_{f,l}$, should balance with the shear stress on side surface of thin slice perpendicular to the longitudinal direction of a whisker with length $2L$ and diameter $2r$ as shown in Fig.2, a differential equation for the longitudinal stresses on whisker is derived as Eq.(1),

$$-d\sigma_{f,l} = \frac{2\tau_{f,l}}{r} dx \quad (1)$$

where $\tau_{i,l}$ is longitudinal shear stress on side surface of thin slice of whisker in Fig.2. Integration of Eq.(1) using a boundary condition, $\sigma_{f,l} = \sigma_m \cos\theta$ at $x = L$, gives following Eq.(2).

$$\sigma_{f,l} = \sigma_m \cos\theta + \frac{2\tau_{i,l}(L-x)}{r} \quad (2)$$

Then the average longitudinal tensile stress on a misaligned whisker is given as,

$$\bar{\sigma}_{f,l} = \sigma_m \cos\theta + \frac{\tau_{i,l} \cdot L}{r} \quad (3)$$

Assuming the longitudinal shear stress on whisker/matrix interface is one half of the tensile stress parallel to the interface, i.e. $\tau_{i,l} = \sigma_m \cos\theta/2$, the Eq.(3) can be expressed as,

$$\bar{\sigma}_{f,l} = \sigma_m \cos\theta + S \cdot \frac{\sigma_m \cos\theta}{2} \quad (4)$$

where S is aspect ratio, which is defined as L/r , of whisker.

At the same time, as the differential transverse tensile stress, $d\sigma_{f,t}$, should balance with the shear stress on side surface of a thin slice perpendicular to the transverse direction of whisker as shown in Fig.3, a force balance equation is derived as Eq.(5).

$$4Lr \cos^2 \phi (\tau_{i,t} + r\tau_{i,t})d\phi = -d\sigma_{f,t} 4Lr \cos\phi \quad (5)$$

Then, a differential equation for the transverse stresses on whisker, $\sigma_{f,t}$, is given as Eq.(6),

$$-d\sigma_{f,t} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{S}\right) \cos\phi \cdot \tau_{i,t} \cdot d\phi \quad (6)$$

where $\tau_{i,t}$ is transverse shear stress on side surface of thin slice of whisker in Fig.3. Integration of Eq.(6) using a boundary condition, $\sigma_{f,t} = \sigma_m \sin\theta$ at $\theta=90^\circ$, gives a following Eq.(7).

$$\sigma_{f,t} = \sigma_m \sin\theta + \left(1 + \frac{1}{S}\right) (1 - \sin\phi) \tau_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

To calculate the average transverse tensile stress on whiskers, the stress multiplied by the slice area, $(2L)(2r\cos\phi)$, was integrated from center to surface and then divided by the integrated area. Since the relative position, y , is represented as $r\sin\phi$, dy is substituted by $r\cos\phi d\phi$, the average transverse tensile stress acting on a whisker can be represented as Eq.(8),

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_{f,t} &= \frac{\int_0^{90} \sigma_{f,t} \cdot 4Lr \cos\phi \cdot r \cos\phi d\phi}{\int_0^{90} 4Lr \cos\phi \cdot r \cos\phi d\phi} \\ &= \sigma_m \cos\phi + \left(\frac{3\pi-4}{3\pi}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S}\right) \cdot \tau_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Assuming the shear stress on side surface is one half of the tensile stress on matrix, i.e. $\tau_{i,t} = \sigma_m \sin \theta / 2$, the Eq.(8) can be rewritten as following Eq.(9),

Fig.3: Schematic diagram showing the transverse stresses on thin slice of a misaligned whisker.

Fig.4: The schematic diagram showing the hemisphere for integration of distributed whiskers in composites.

$$\bar{\sigma}_{f,t} = \sigma_m \sin \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \frac{\sigma_m \sin \theta}{2} \quad (9)$$

The stress transferred on whisker along loading axis, σ_f , can be calculated by the vector summation of average longitudinal tensile stress and average transverse tensile stress as following,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_f &= \bar{\sigma}_{f,l} \cdot \cos \theta + \bar{\sigma}_{f,t} \cdot \sin \theta \\ &= \sigma_m \cos^2 \theta + \frac{S}{2} \sigma_m \cos^2 \theta + \sigma_m \sin^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \frac{\sigma_m \sin^2 \theta}{2} \\ &= \sigma_m \left[1 + \frac{S}{2} \cos^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \sin^2 \theta \right] + \sigma_m \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

By using the rule-of-mixture for composites, a generalized shear-lag model is proposed to calculate the stress on composites with misaligned whiskers as following Eq.(11).

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &= V_f \sigma_f + V_m \sigma_m \\ &= V_f \sigma_m \left[1 + \frac{S}{2} \cos^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{2} \right] + V_m \sigma_m \\ &= V_f \sigma_m \frac{1}{2} \left[S \cos^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \sin^2 \theta \right] + \sigma_m \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

From the modified shear-lag model [8], the stress on composites with perfectly aligned whiskers is suggested as Eq.(12).

$$\sigma = V_f \sigma_m \frac{S}{2} + \sigma_m \quad (12)$$

Comparing Eq.(11) and Eq.(12), a new parameter named effective aspect ratio, S_{eff} , for a misaligned whisker is defined as following Eq.(13).

$$S_{\text{eff}} = S \cos^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \sin^2 \theta \quad (13)$$

Load Transfer on Distributed Whiskers

The density of whiskers aligned with misorientation angle, θ , in extruded composite decreases exponentially with increasing θ [10,11]. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the whisker density function, $F(\theta)$, is expressed as following Eq.(14),

$$F(\theta) = A \cdot \exp(-K\theta) \quad (14)$$

where A and K are constants related to the degree of whisker alignment. The effective aspect ratio contributed by the whiskers aligned with misorientation angle between θ and $\theta+d\theta$, as shown in Fig.4, could be calculated as following equation.

$$dS_{\text{eff}} = S_{\text{eff}}(\theta) \cdot F(\theta) \cdot (2\pi \sin \theta) \cdot d\theta \quad (15)$$

Then, the effective aspect ratio contributed by the whole distributed whiskers along the longitudinal direction of composites is calculated as,

$$S_{\text{eff},l} = \int_0^{90} S_{\text{eff}}(\theta) \cdot F(\theta) \cdot 2\pi \sin \theta \cdot d\theta \quad (16)$$

On the other hand, the effective aspect ratio contributed by the whole distributed whiskers along the transverse direction of composite is calculated as Eq.(17) including the two geometrical angles, η and ϕ , shown in Fig.5.

$$S_{\text{eff},t} = 4 \int_0^{90} \int_0^{90} S_{\text{eff}}(\eta) \cdot F(\cos^{-1}(\sin \eta \cdot \cos \phi)) \cdot \sin \eta \cdot d\eta \cdot d\phi \quad (17)$$

The value of $S_{\text{eff},t}$ can be calculated numerically as a function of degree of alignment, K , and average aspect ratio, S , of whiskers.

Fig.5: The schematic diagram showing the geometrical angles related to the alignment of a whisker

Fig.6: The variation of effective aspect ratio of a whisker with varying the misorientation angle, θ

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The calculated effective aspect ratio of a misaligned whisker using the Eq.(13) decreased rapidly with increasing the misorientation angle, θ , from 0° to 90° as shown in Fig.6. The effective aspect ratio of a whisker with larger aspect ratio decreased more rapidly than that with smaller aspect ratio with increasing the misorientation angle. The decrease in effective aspect ratio with increasing the misorientation angle in Fig.6 indicates that the load transfer efficiency decreases and the strengthening effect of misaligned whisker reduces with increasing the misorientation angle.

Fig.7 shows the variation of the effective aspect ratio with varying the aspect ratio of a misaligned whisker having misorientation angle θ . When the whisker is perfectly aligned parallel to the loading axis, i.e. the misorientation angle is 0° , the effective aspect ratio increased linearly with increasing the aspect ratio of whisker. When the misorientation angle is 45° , the effective aspect ratio increased non-linearly with increasing the aspect ratio and was smaller than that with misorientation angle of 0° . However, when the misorientation angle is 90° , i.e. the whisker is aligned perpendicular to the loading axis, the effective aspect ratio decreased with increasing the aspect ratio of whisker. This is because the end surface of whisker mainly contribute to the load transfer to whisker with misorientation angle of 90° and the fraction of end surface area decreased with increasing the aspect ratio.

Fig. 8 shows the variation of effective aspect ratios of distributed whiskers in longitudinal and transverse directions with varying the degree of alignment, K , when the average aspect ratio of whiskers is 3 and 10. The effective aspect ratio in longitudinal direction increased, while that in transverse direction decreased with increasing the K value. The effective aspect ratio was sensitively varied within the K value ranged from -10 to +10, while showed almost constant value when the K value above 10 or below -10. When the K value is 10, the amount of whiskers misaligned more than 30° was calculated only 0.5%. This indicates almost perfect alignment of whiskers when the K value is 10 or higher. As the most extruded metal matrix

composites showed K value less than 5, the effective aspect ratio was sensitively dependent on the degree of alignment in addition to the average aspect ratio of whiskers.

Fig. 7: The variation of effective aspect ratio with varying the aspect ratio of a whisker with misorientation angle θ

Fig. 8: The variation of the effective aspect ratio of distributed whiskers in longitudinal and transverse directions with varying the degree of alignment, K , of distributed whisker.

The tensile strength of metal matrix composites along longitudinal and transverse directions can be represented by the generalized shear-lag model by substituting the effective aspect ratio, S_{eff} , into the aspect ratio, S , expressed as following equation,

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m \left[V_f \cdot \frac{S_{\text{eff}}}{2} + V_m \right] \quad (18)$$

where σ_m is the average stress on matrix, and V_f and V_m are the volume fractions of whisker and matrix, respectively. To examine the validity of the concept on the generalized shear-lag model, the tensile strengths calculated from the Eq.(18) using the effective aspect ratios in longitudinal and transverse directions were compared with the measured tensile strengths[7] and calculated values by the modified shear-lag model. The average aspect ratio was assumed to be 4 as indicated in the paper, and the degree of whisker alignment, K , was assumed to be 4, which is a typical value for whiskers in extruded metal matrix composites. Table 1 compares the measured tensile strengths of SiCw/Al composites with the calculated values based on both the generalized shear-lag model and the modified shear-lag model, respectively. The calculated tensile strengths from the generalized shear-lag model showed more similar values with the measured tensile strengths of SiCw/Al composites in longitudinal and transverse directions than those calculated from the modified shear-lag model. This indicates that the load transfer efficiency of whiskers was analyzed more accurately by the proposed generalized shear-lag model, which considers the load transfer at

side and end surface of misaligned whiskers, because the whiskers are not perfectly aligned in metal matrix composites.

Table 1: The measured and calculated tensile strengths of SiCw/Al composites in longitudinal and transverse directions.

		Measured Tensile Strength (MPa)	Calculated by Generalized Shear-lag Model (MPa)	Calculated by Modified Shear-lag Model (MPa)
20% SiCw/6061Al -T6	Longitudinal	447	472	500
	Transverse	409	402	393
	L/T Ratio	1.10	1.17	1.27
20% SiCw/2124Al -T6	Longitudinal	524	520	551
	Transverse	466	442	433
	L/T Ratio	1.12	1.18	1.27

CONCLUSIONS

The load transfer efficiency of a misaligned whisker was analyzed assuming that both the shear stresses on side surface and the normal stress on end surface of whisker contribute to the load transfer from matrix. Considering the load transfer contribution of distributed whiskers in composite, a new parameter of effective aspect ratio, S_{eff} , was proposed to represent the load transfer efficiency of misaligned whiskers in composites as a function of average aspect ratio and misalignment angle. A generalized shear-lag model was proposed as a function of effective aspect ratio to estimate the tensile strength of metal matrix composites. It is confirmed that the generalized shear-lag model estimate the tensile strength of SiCw/Al composites more accurately compared to the modified shear-lag model in longitudinal and transverse directions.

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